

The correlation between parental education level and emotional disorders among female adolescents in high schools in Surabaya

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Abstract

According to WHO data (2022), in 2019, 1 in every 8 people, or approximately 970 million individuals worldwide, lived with mental disorders, including anxiety and depression. Poor emotional conditions can affect an individual's physical health, with one of the impacts on female adolescents being irregular menstrual cycles. Female adolescents can detect emotional disorders early, which highlights the importance of environmental support, particularly the role of parents. Mothers with higher education levels are likely to play a significant role in family decision-making.

This study aimed to examine the correlation between parental education levels and emotional disorders among female adolescents in high schools in Surabaya. The study employed a quantitative analysis method with an observational design and a cross-sectional approach. Data were collected from female adolescents aged 15–17 years in high schools in Surabaya using cluster random sampling. The data were analyzed using the Chi-Square test.

The results showed p-values of 0.174 and 0.350 (p-value > 0.05), indicating no significant correlation between parental education levels and emotional disorders among female adolescents aged 15–17 years in high schools in Surabaya. Future research should further explore factors related to emotional disorders to reduce the prevalence of such cases.

Keywords: Parental education level; Emotional disorders; Female adolescents; Physical health

1. Introduction

According to WHO data (2022), in 2019, 1 in every 8 individuals, or approximately 970 million people worldwide, lived with mental disorders, including anxiety and depression. The 2018 Basic Health Research (Riset Kesehatan Dasar, Riskesdas) reported that over 19 million Indonesians aged over 15 years experienced emotional mental disorders, and more than 12 million suffered from depression. Furthermore, Riskesdas 2018 highlighted that the prevalence of emotional disorders among individuals aged ≥ 15 years in East Java was 6.8%, compared to the national average of 9.8%.

Previous studies have shown that most adolescents aged 15–19 years in East Java experience behavioral and emotional disorders (U.K. Aziz et al., 2021). According to the 2007 Basic Health Research, the prevalence of severe mental disorders, such as schizophrenia, in East Java was 1.4%, while Surabaya recorded a prevalence of 0.2%. Emotional mental disorders (e.g., anxiety, depression) were recorded at 35% in East Java and 18.8% in Surabaya.

Kristina (2020) conducted a study on high school students in Surabaya, including Hidayatul Ummah Senior High School, State Vocational High School 10, State Senior High School 22, State Senior High School 15, and State Senior High School 19 in Surabaya. The study revealed abnormal emotional disorders in 18% of students during the initial measurement,

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which increased to 24% during follow-up. Various emotional disorders can be influenced by multiple factors, and if not addressed properly, they can lead to undesirable outcomes.

Purnamasari et al. (2023) identified family environment as one of the factors influencing emotional mental disorders among high school students. The family environment includes the role of mothers. According to Setiawati et al. (2017), women with higher education levels tend to have a more significant role in family decision-making.

Based on the aforementioned phenomena, this study aims to investigate the correlation between parental education levels and emotional disorders among female adolescents in high schools in Surabaya.

2. Material and methods

This study employed a quantitative method with a cross-sectional approach. The objective was to examine the correlation between parental education levels and emotional disorders among female adolescents aged 15–17 years in high schools in Surabaya. The study was conducted at Hidayatul Ummah Senior High School, State Vocational High School 10, State Senior High School 22, State Senior High School 15, and State Senior High School 19 in Surabaya. The population consisted of female adolescents aged 15–17 years, with a sample size of 90 respondents selected using a cluster random sampling technique.

Data collection was carried out from October to November 2024 using questionnaires that included demographic characteristics and emotional disorder assessments. To evaluate emotional conditions, the researchers utilized the PSC-17 (Pediatric Symptom Checklist-17). Bivariate analysis was conducted using the Chi-Square test to examine the correlations between variables, with a significance level set at 5% ($\alpha = 0.05$).

3. Results and discussion

The study was conducted from October to November 2024 at Hidayatul Ummah Senior High School, State Vocational High School 10, State Senior High School 22, State Senior High School 15, and State Senior High School 19 in Surabaya, involving 90 respondents.

Table 1 Frequency Distribution of Parental Education Levels

Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Mother's education		
Elementary School	13	14.4
Junior High School	14	15.6
Senior High School	46	51.1
Diploma/Bachelor	17	18.9
Total	90	100%
Father's education		
Elementary School	16	17.8
Junior High School	12	13.3
Senior High School	42	46.7
Diploma/Bachelor	20	22.2
Total	90	100%

The table above shows that the highest level of maternal education is up to high school, with 46 (51.1%) respondents, and the highest level of paternal education is also up to high school, with 42 (46.7%) respondents. This finding is supported by another study conducted by Zulfitri (2017), which found that the majority of mothers of grade V students had a high school education, with 18 individuals (37.5%). Additionally, a study by Aditya et al. (2023) reported that the majority of respondents had a high school education, with 63 individuals (64.9%).

The prevalence of parents with a high school education can be influenced by several factors. Factors contributing to individuals not continuing their education from high school to higher education include the environment, family economy, influence from others, and lack of parental attention. Society is considered the third educational factor after family and school, as it can influence an individual's education level by shaping their lifestyle. Another factor is the family's economic condition; a low family income can prevent parents from continuing their children's education or, in some cases, force them to stop their children's schooling. Furthermore, a lack of parental attention can lead to poor academic performance or cause children to decide to drop out of school (Zulkarnaian and Sari, 2019)

Table 2 Frequency Distribution of Emotional Conditions

Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Not Bothered	39	43.3
Disturbed	51	56.7
Total	90	100%

Based on Table 2 above regarding emotional conditions, it can be concluded that the majority of female adolescents are at risk of emotional disorders, with 51 respondents (56.7%) showing such conditions. This finding is in line with a study conducted by Sitepu et al. (2024) on children aged 4-17 years at the Pasar Minggu Health Center, which reported that 35 out of 52 children (67.3%) experienced emotional disorders. Additionally, a study by Azzahro and Sari (2021) on high school students in Jember found that 79 out of 158 students were at risk of emotional disorders.

Table 3 The Correlation between Parental Education Level and Emotional Disorders

Last Education	Emotional Condition				Total	P Value
	Not Bothered		Disturbed			
	N	%	N	%		
Mother						0.174
Elementary school	3	23	10	77	13	
Junior high school	8	57	6	43	14	
Senior High School	22	48	24	52	46	
College	5	29	12	71	17	
Total	38	157	52	243	90	
Father						0.350
Elementary school	8	50	8	50	16	
Junior high school	6	50	6	50	12	
Senior High School	19	45	23	55	42	
College	5	25	15	75	20	
Total	38	170	52	230	90	

The results of the chi-square analysis regarding the correlation between parental education level and emotional disorders showed p-values of 0.174 and 0.350 (p-value > 0.05), indicating that there is no significant correlation between parental education level and emotional disorders in female adolescents at senior high schools in Surabaya. This finding is supported by a study conducted by Ningsih et al. (2024), which concluded that there is no correlation between parental education and mental disorders in senior high school students.

This can occur because emotional disorders in adolescents are influenced by several factors, such as the school environment and peer correlations. The school environment is where students engage in educational activities to understand knowledge, develop attitudes, and acquire life skills, both inside and outside the classroom, while adhering

to the established rules and educational systems. This ensures that learning proceeds according to the intended goals. Peer correlations have a significant impact on shaping the direction of an adolescent's life. Peer interactions play a crucial role in fostering various social skills. Adolescents who interact with negative peers tend to develop negative behaviors, attitudes, and life goals. On the other hand, adolescents who engage with positive peers, where a group consistently provides encouragement, support, and opportunities for positive self-actualization, are more likely to develop positive attitudes (Purnamasari et al., 2023).

The prevalence of emotional disorders among adolescents can be influenced by several factors, as mentioned above. If not addressed promptly, emotional disorders in female adolescents can have adverse effects on their physical health, one of which is their menstrual cycle. Parents play a crucial role in monitoring their children's emotional well-being, as they have the opportunity to spend a significant amount of time with their children.

4. Conclusion

This study concludes that there is no correlation between the parents highest education level and emotional disorders in female adolescents in high schools in Surabaya. Additionally, the study shows that the majority of respondents (46.7%), who are female adolescents in high schools in Surabaya, have mothers with a high school education level. Furthermore, the majority of respondents (57.8%) in this study, who are female adolescents in high schools in Surabaya, experience emotional disorders.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

There was no conflict of interest.

Statement of ethical approval

The Research and Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Airlangga, Indonesia, approved this study with letter number 127/EC/KEPK/FKUA/2024, valid from October 13, 2024, to October 13, 2025.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all parents of participants included in the study.

Reference

- [1] Aditya, A. N., Indriati, G., and Fitri, A. (2023) 'The Realtionship Between Parental Role and Mental-Emotional Development', *Jurnal Keperawatan Profesional*, 11(1), pp. 1–19. doi: 10.33650/jkp.v11i1.5536.
- [2] Alam, F. A. (2020) 'The Influence of Parental Education Level and Attention on Student Learning Discipline at SMP Negeri 3 Barru', *Jurnal Bimbingan dan Konseling*, 7(1), pp. 1–11. Available at: <https://jurnal.stkipmb.ac.id/index.php/bkmb/article/view/48>.
- [3] Azzahro, E. A., and Sari, J. D. E. (2021) 'Psychosocial Factors and Depression Incidence in Adolescents (A Study on 12th Grade Students of SMA XY Jember)', *Journal of Community Mental Health and Public Policy*, 3(2), pp. 69–77. doi: 10.51602/cmhp.v3i2.54.
- [4] Aziz, U. K., Lutfiya, I., and Sulaiman, I. (2021) 'Description of Behavioral and Emotional Disorders in Adolescents Aged 10-24 Based on Sociodemographic Factors (Analysis of Susenas Data 2015)', *Journal of Biostatistics and Demographic Dynamics*, 1(2), pp. 62. doi: <https://doi.org/10.19184/biograph-i.v1i2.27873>.
- [5] Kristina, D. N. A. (2020) *Analysis of Mental Health Conditions as an Effort to Prevent Risky Behavior in High School Adolescents in Surabaya*. Universitas Airlangga.
- [6] Ningsih, et al. (2024) 'The Relationship Between Parental Education Level and Income on Mental Health of Students in Bukittinggi', *Jurnal Penelitian Perawat Profesional*, 9(1), pp. 188–196.

- [7] Purnamasari, Y., Fitri, N., and Mardiana, N. (2023) 'Factors Affecting Emotional and Mental Disorders in High School Adolescents', *Jurnal Penelitian Perawat Profesional*, 5(2), pp. 609–616. doi: 10.37287/jppp.v5i2.1527.
- [8] Kementerian Kesehatan RI (2019) *Riskesmas 2018*. Jakarta: Kementerian Kesehatan RI.
- [9] Setiawati, E., Malihah, E., and Komariah, S. (2018) 'Factors Affecting Highly Educated Women as Decision-Makers in Families in Isola Village', *Sosietas*, 7(1), pp. 329–334. doi: 10.17509/sosietas.v7i1.10345.
- [10] Zulfitria (2018) 'The Influence of Parental Education Background on Student Learning Achievement in Primary Schools', *Holistika*, 2, pp. 1–8. Available at: <https://jurnal.umj.ac.id/index.php/holistika/article/download/2872/2331>.
- [11] Zulkarnain, Z., and Sari, M. (2019) 'Factors Affecting Children's Education Level in Dusun Patre, Mangkung Village, Praya Barat Subdistrict', *Society*, 10(1), pp. 53–69. doi: 10.20414/society.v10i1.1488.
- [12] World Health Organization (2022) *Mental Disorders*. Available at: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/mentaldisorders> (Accessed: 9 June 2024).